

Name of beneficiary: OKSTAL (UK) Ltd. Hungarian Branch

Name and code number of the call for proposals: Prototype, product, technology and service development, GINOP-2.1.7-15

Project title: Creation of a super-clean antimicrobial healthcare clothing system using nanotechnology

Project identification number: GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-00740

Amount of contracted support: HUF 45,528,280

Support rate: 62.81

Planned completion date of the project: 2019.10.14.

Brief description of the project

The OKSTAL project was created with the clear goal of bringing 21st century textile material technology to segments of the textile industry that have been slow to develop and have received little research and development focus (e.g., healthcare uniforms, medical gowns). The professionals who form the backbone of the company have extensive experience in major light industry projects (leather, outdoor, military, product design, branding, management), so the basic idea is to expand from material design and manufacturing to complete product design and sales in the future. The concept of vertical product management, i.e. keeping everything in-house, is not necessarily new, but in this sector it has so far only been typical of made-to-measure sub-sectors (e.g. haute couture, bespoke tailoring) producing extremely expensive products that are not designed with functionality in mind. The benefits of vertical integration include the ability to thoroughly consider products, maintain their functionality, and clearly improve quality while ensuring a high degree of control over product development processes. The organizational goal of our company is to eventually separate the future divisions of product development, product design, management, and manufacturing to an appropriate extent, while maintaining a high level of product quality. The company's development opportunities include exploring new market segments and further areas of application for the technology, alongside the continuous development and operation of the manufacturing processes to be launched at the end of the product development cycle.

OKSTAL (UK) Ltd. Hungarian Branch applied for the relevant funds under GINOP-2.1.7-15 Prototype, Product, Technology and Service Development tender with the aim of developing a clothing system based on scientific research results in nanotechnology, primarily for healthcare applications, with a range of special antimicrobial and liquid-repellent properties and a design developed with the involvement of a discerning professional audience.

brings user experience to a sector where this has not been a consideration until now. With the support the received, we have carried out the following professional activities in the textile industry:

- Design of the raw material (griége), development of its wearing comfort and textile appearance, taking into account the requirements of material technology.
- Designing the weave style (plain, twill or satin) and carrying out post-processing methods.
- Preliminary planning of finishing processes (size retention, mercerization, dyeing).
- Prototyping of the material.
- Material testing (EN, ISO, and DIN testing) to ensure that the material itself meets all requirements for its intended use.
- PCS (Product Concept Sketch), i.e. product concept development
- Compilation of detailed plans into a product
- Early adopters (discussion process) were involved, i.e. healthcare professionals whose expert opinions were integrated into the product, as they will be the primary users of the new technology.
- Development of concept designs for the preparation of pattern drawings and manufacturing technology documents.
- Preparation of patterns based on the drawings and concepts developed during the design process, with the help of a highly experienced professional skilled in tailoring technology and solutions.
- Checking the finished patterns against the details of the original concept.
- Use of the technologies available in the prototyping workshop to accurately produce the sewing patterns (e.g., pleats, gluing, lamination, stitch types, technical specifics of buttoning, heat transfer).
- Preparation of cutting prototypes. After the final cutting patterns and technological coordination, the first cutting prototypes are prepared, not from the final material. Cutting coordination, actual coordination of material requirements and panel distribution, pre-qualification for production.
- Review of samples with early adopter professional audience.
- Parts pattern making.
- Production of non-material-specific components.
- Prototyping and material-accurate pattern making.
- Sampling
- 2nd prototype copies.
- Development of PIC (Product Image Concept)

The above activities were carried out in-house or with the involvement of carefully selected contractors, using high-performance computers and special software.

The work of external experts and partners was subject to continuous professional supervision, which was carried out by two developers and one marketing employee, depending on the task.

In addition to this, we prepared the process of turning the prototypes into future products. We laid the foundations for the future market presence of our prototypes by conducting market research and other market analysis tasks. We carried out our work under continuous professional supervision and consultation, taking into account all relevant regulations, and strove to position our products in the best possible way for their future market entry. We participated in one of Hungary's most prestigious exhibitions. The HUNGAROMED Healthcare and Medical Technology Exhibition and Conference is Hungary's only comprehensive healthcare forum, where innovative companies, accredited training courses and the latest developments in professional policy await visitors every year. The event provides an excellent opportunity for manufacturers, distributors, customers, and doctors, pharmacists, and healthcare professionals who use the devices to meet.

As a result of the work carried out, sample textiles were produced and their complete technical documentation was also completed. Finished medical uniform designs and concepts were prepared for the manufacturing technology descriptions. Documents containing sewing patterns and sewing manufacturing technology descriptions were prepared, on the basis of which prototypes of the finished medical uniforms, their technical drawings, and complete documentation of the sewing manufacturing technology were produced.

The fundamental objective of this development was to create a novel, forward-looking, nanotechnology-based medical uniform technology that significantly reduces the risk of infection for healthcare workers and the patients they come into contact with. In addition, their production, properties, and cleaning requirements significantly reduce the environmental impact for both existing contract textile service providers and hospital procurement. Thanks to fluorine-free DWRF technology incorporated into the fabric at the fiber level, the special fiber structure of the raw materials can be made repellent to medium and high viscosity liquids. The technology is based on a nanoscale solution, which gives it natural antibacterial properties as well as antiviral and antifungal treatment. This represents a significant risk reduction compared to currently available techniques. What's more, the resulting textile technology is so cost-effective that washing frequency can be increased by 3-5 times and service life extended several times over, reducing the overall environmental footprint of the solution to a fraction of what it would otherwise be.

We expect several positive effects as a result of the project. The potential of the developed technology allows for a wide range of applications. The properties of the individual raw material groups (griages) can be modified to suit the area of application, while retaining all the advantages of nanotechnology-based material processing. In short, we can produce both flexible trousers and stiffer coats. Everything depends on market demand. In addition, a color scale is being developed based on the technology developed, which will allow for further customization when the product is launched on the market.

The more basic properties that can be customized during the material development process (elasticity, colors, appearance, composition), the more likely the product will be successful when it hits the market. During the development process, we focused on as many of these possible properties as possible while retaining the repellent and antimicrobial advantages of nanotechnology.

All these positive aspects contribute to the successful and professionally high-level operation of OKSTAL (UK) Ltd. Hungarian Branch. They contribute to an increase in sales revenue by enabling us to work in professionally outstanding conditions.

Project results:

Among the planned outcomes of the development, we have implemented the use of the completed nanotechnology fabric technology in a range of healthcare garments featuring different cuts and materials. This is due to the different requirements of the various areas of application.

We focused on developing the following marketable product groups:

- medical gowns
- medical trousers
- medical uniforms
- nurses' uniforms
- Shirts and tunics for all types of healthcare workers

The aim of our development is to create a new, forward-looking, nanotechnology-based healthcare uniform technology that significantly reduces the risk of infection for healthcare workers and the patients they come into contact with. In addition, their production, properties and cleaning requirements significantly reduce the environmental impact for both existing contract textile service providers and hospital procurement.

Thanks to fluorine-free DWR technology incorporated into the fabric at the fiber level, the special fiber structure of the raw materials can be made durable and strong, repelling liquids ranging from medium to high viscosity. The technology is based on a nanoscale solution, so in addition to its natural antibacterial properties, it can also be treated with antiviral and antifungal agents. This represents a significant risk reduction compared to currently available techniques. The textile technology developed in this way is also so cost-effective that the washing frequency can be increased by a factor of 3-5 and the service life extended several times over, thus reducing the environmental footprint of the solution to a fraction of what it would otherwise be.

The potential of the developed technology allows for a wide range of applications. The properties of the individual raw material groups (griages) can be adapted to the area of application.

change them while retaining all the advantages of nanotechnology-based material handling. In short, we can produce flexible trousers and stiffer coats. It all depends on the requirements that arise during the research phase or later in terms of market demands. In addition, the technology developed can be used to create a color palette, which will allow for further customization when the product is eventually launched on the market. The more basic properties that can be customized during material development (elasticity, colors, appearance, composition), the more likely the product will be successful when it is eventually launched on the market. During the development process, we would like to explore as many of these possible properties as possible while retaining the repellent and antimicrobial advantages of nanotechnology.

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Attachment:

1. prototype_technical_description_TROUSERS_PDF
2. prototype_technical_description_TUNIC_PDF
3. material_testing_reports_EGYBEN_PDF